

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BERU****FIRST NAME: TARIKU****COUNTRY: ETHIOPIA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The student used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references
The author used Zotero to insert references.
The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).
My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%
The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

Key concepts with a page number in the text (then bold them in your RP)

1. Basic steps before starting essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-9)
2. Structure in essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 10)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

After obtaining guidance from Euclid University and my instructor pertaining to my Doctor of Philosophy in Public Health (DPIH) journey, I downloaded and went through the attached documents and familiarized myself with the information. I repeatedly read the ACA-401/ACA-401D Period 1 course pack prior to commencing response paper one (RP1) writing. I have also watched and listened to the video presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and well understood the rules of styles, referencing, punctuation, paragraph, and how to save, upload and send to my instructor. The course pack was revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck to introduce good academic essay writing to Euclid University students emphasizing essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, and informing students rules of styles. It was also explained in the course pack about the three main structures of an academic essay, in addition, to other very important information, like illustrations of students' response paper reviews.

Despite reading the course pack and other shared documents, as well as watching the video, it took some time to conceptualize what to write about and it was also a bit difficult for me where and how to start once I understood what to write about.

In this period-1 of the response paper, I have chosen five concepts and tried to briefly discuss and reflected on the course pack that comprises some **basic steps before starting an essay, structure in essay writing, some rules of thumb for writing a paper, plagiarism, and style guide.**

2) BASIC STEPS BEFORE STARTING ESSAY WRITING

The essence of pursuing basic steps before starting academic essay writing is clearly stated in ACA-401/ACA-401D Period 1 course pack though the steps are not rigidly linear. In the course pack, it was indicated that early start-up, defining the question and analysis of tasks, and drafting the preliminary plan are the basic steps we should follow before starting essay writing (EUCLID 2021,7). The document magnifies the need of taking adequate time to read and research the topic, think, and write the first draft during this first step of the start-up of an essay.

I am highly impressed with the explanation given in the course pack about giving adequate time to think and research the topic and development of the preliminary plan as these activities are so essential for a good academic essay. Most of us lack enough understanding about the essence of giving adequate time for the early phase of academic essay writing. However, as clearly indicated in the course pack, allocating adequate time is crucial in academic essay writing and an early start enables the writer to get enough time to execute all preliminary tasks as early as possible.

The ECULID course pack further describes the preliminary tasks before starting the essay. Preliminary tasks are activities starting essay writing which include the development of the initial plan, initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic, and reading and researching the topic as well as organizing the ideas (EUCLID 2021, 7-9).

I comprehend very important notes from the explanation made in the course pack under the above concept like the essence of early start-up, thorough reading and researching on the topic as well as organizing ideas before starting academic essay writing without procrastination.

3) STRUCTURE IN ESSAY WRITING

Emphasizing the production of the first draft during the actual essay writing, ACA-401/ACA-401D RP1 adequately clarifies the three main structures in academic essay writing categorized as an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). In the first part, the introduction flows from general to specific and the writer provides a brief orientation of the topic area as well as all main ideas are briefly explained including the road map of the essay. The course pack, in addition, states that the body part of the essay is the one in which we develop discussions and answer questions, show our knowledge of the material we read, argue and give our evidence for the argument with relevant examples, and so on. The third and conclusion part of the essay moves from specific to general by restating the answer to the question, indicating possible

implications and future directions for future studies as well as summarizing the main points.

Equally important, I appreciate the brief explanation regarding the contents in the body paragraphs. It was stated that each paragraph discusses one main idea, and this paragraph should explain the idea or the topic starting with the topic sentence, supporting sentence, evidence, and analysis part (EUCLID 2021, 11).

In general, I have upgraded my little knowledge by reading detailed elements of the above concept in ACA-401/ACA-401D Period 1, and this knowledge will surely help me in the subsequent works of my academic journey.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPER

As a matter of fact, any academic essay lacks quality and integrity if the paper does not entail all important points mentioned under this concept. I have noted from this section of the course pack the essence of stating the paper's main thesis from the beginning and focusing on the important aspects of the theories being discussed, writing clearly and to the point without making the writing boring (EUCLID 2021, 13).

In addition, I have also affirmed from the course that any assertion for views of the author's idea should be supported with evidence that is obtained from credible and relevant passages. Limiting the number of quotations and using quotations if only the passage has a significant role in the paper and the worthlessness of submitting of paper congested with quotations is briefly explained. The books and papers we are reading might have been reviewed by many scholars, and we should critically and repeatedly read them to get inside the conception, view them seriously and argue against ourselves to avoid misinterpretations (EUCLID 2021, 13-14)

It was further explained about plagiarism that plagiarism might happen if one uses direct words from a source without quotation marks, and plagiarism can be avoided by using quotation marks, paraphrasing as well as proper citations (EUCLID 2021, 14)

In summary, I have noted from this discussion that my papers will be improved by investing a short time in reading and editing, and I believe that my doctoral journey in public health will be smooth as long as I correctly apply the rules of thumb among others.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is defined in EUCLID (2021, 34) as “When the writer uses the source of information without giving credit to the author of the information.” It is clearly indicated in ACA-401/ACA-401D RP1 that plagiarism is wrong and unethical whether it is employed intentionally or unintentionally. I also noted from the course pack that not mentioning the source is a serious academic offense that may result in serious consequences. So, the only solution to avoid plagiarism is to properly and consistently

cite the source that information came from by text citation and listing the work cited at the end of the paper (EUCLID 2021, 34-35).

From the explanation in the course pack, I noted that Chicago (Turabian) rule suggests putting the author's name who wrote the passage and the page number from which the information was taken as an in-text citation. Therefore, I understand that the common things that should be cited using in-text citations are quotations and paraphrases which means, a quotation is the exact word of the author, and a paraphrase is the idea of the author produced on the topic but written in the current writer's words.

Further explanation is made in ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack about quotation and paraphrasing which clarifies the blurred understanding that I have before. Accordingly, limiting the use of quotations in the research and using them when only necessary was highlighted. It was also emphasized that in paraphrasing, our writing style should be different from the author's one, we should use our own words, and the information we give should be an accurate representation of the original one and, proper citation of the source (EUCLID 2021, 36).

6) STYLE GUIDE

According to EUCLID (2021, 41), the style guide is "A means of documenting your approach as a writer as to certain elements of writing style that needs to be consistent." The availability of published guidelines is very important for the writer not to follow his personal style, but rather to apply that of the company or University styles related to the writing.

In the past, I have experience using the American Psychological Association (APA) and Harvard rules and in this course pack, I understand Chicago (Turabian) rule which is recommended by EUCLID for this course as well as other international styles. I recognized that the style guide is a very important tool for my paper works and for fulfilling my aim and for achieving my DIPH goal. It will enable me to maintain the coherency and constancy of my writing.

On the other hand, I have objections and argue why all companies and Universities fail to agree to use one or two established style rules rather than having many authoritative sources to avoid confusion.

7) CONCLUSION

As an entry point, the effort I made to write my first response paper (RP1) by reading documents shared by EUCLID University for the RP1 stimulated me to read the subsequent documents sent by the University and proceed with respective assignments (responses). In ACA-401/ACA-401D RP1, basic and comprehensive concepts and information were explained which really showed me my knowledge gaps and guided me to eagerly read the subsequent EUCLID documents as well as others. In my opinion, the

strategy that EUCLID University uses especially sending reading materials to the students and receiving their response papers subsequently and reviewing and sending them back is so appreciable. It is easy to imagine what kind of dissertation I can produce by going through all these reading materials, writing all these response papers, and receiving all the feedback from my instructors.

In general, I got basic knowledge of international academic and professional paper writing basics from ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack. The course pack has well explained the main contents of good academic essay writing emphasizing basic steps before starting essay writing, steps and structures in essay writing, some rules of thumb, a study guide, and plagiarism among others.

REFERENCES

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